

Towards Open-Set NLP-Based Multi-Level Planning for Robotic Tasks

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Featured Application: Robotic tabletop manipulation of objects using commands in natural language.

Abstract: This paper outlines a conceptual design for a multi-level natural language-based planning system and describes a demonstrator. The main goal of the demonstrator is to serve as a proof-of-concept by accomplishing end-to-end execution in a real-world environment, and showing a novel way of interfacing an LLM-based planner with open-set semantic maps. The target use-case is executing sequences of tabletop pick-and-place operations using an industrial robot arm and RGB-D camera. The demonstrator processes unstructured user prompts, produces high-level action plans, queries a map for object positions and grasp poses using open-set semantics, then uses the resulting outputs to parametrize and execute a sequence of action primitives. In this paper, the overall system structure, high-level planning using language models, low-level planning through action and motion primitives, as well as the implementation of two different environment modeling schemes—2.5 or fully 3-dimensional—are described in detail. The impacts of quantizing image embeddings on object recall are assessed and high-level planner performance is evaluated using a small reference scene data set. We observe that, for the simple constrained test command data set, the high-level planner is able to achieve a total success rate of 96.40%, while the semantic maps exhibit maximum recall rates of 94.69% and 92.29% for the 2.5d and 3d versions, respectively.

Keywords: robotics; open-set semantics; SLAM; vision–language model (VLM); perception

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1. Introduction

Allowing human operators to seamlessly interface with robotic control systems using unstructured natural language has been a long-held goal in artificial intelligence, quite possibly since the field's inception. Advances made in the field of machine learning over the past decade have opened the door to many exciting developments in this respect. Of great interest are transformer models for sequence prediction tasks [1], which may form the backbone of large language models (LLM) when applied in a pure natural language processing (NLP) context, or be combined with techniques for transforming multiple data modalities into the same latent embedding vector space to produce multi-modal—e.g., vision–language (VLM)—models [2].

Traditionally, planning in robotics has been treated as a search problem in a configuration space [3]. This has advantages where the robot's environment can be understood analytically. However, when dealing with unstructured information such as a command given in natural language, explicitly expressing the task as a classic search problem becomes intractable. Recent work has leveraged large language models to act as high-level planners [4] and multi-modal vision–language–action models produce low-level control outputs directly [5]. The direct control approach is limited to acting on the information directly available to the trained model for inference, whereas the high-level planner can be more readily integrated with existing robot control software, utilize reusable workspace models with pre-computed constraints, and produce human-readable intermediate results.

We seek to develop an architecture for a high-level planner-based robot control system which can start with a natural language prompt and produce a successfully executed sequence of motions producing the desired effect in the physical world. The goal of this article is therefore to demonstrate that it is possible to accomplish the above requirement through the implementation of the following three sub-systems:

- A **high-level planning (HLP)** pipeline turning natural language commands into a structured plan and extract relevant queries for particular information from the raw text;
- A **low-level planning (LLP)** system capable of executing each action in the plan extracted from the command by the HLP;
- A **semantic map** of the environment that can be queried using natural language concepts obtained from the original command.

Therefore, we outline an architecture for combining these subsystems into a robot control system. We implement an instance of this architecture as a proof-of-concept demonstrator, which can perform sequences of pick-and-place actions involving objects in a tabletop scene. We use an industrial robot arm as our actuator and a depth camera for perception. The demonstrator consists of an LLM-based HLP, an LLP system implementing a skill set of discrete actions, and either a static 2.5D semantic depth map or a fully 3D octree gridmap. We show successful end-to-end execution.

In addition, quantization of the open-set image embeddings is assessed, as this provides a mitigation for the potentially prohibitive memory and network bandwidth costs of transferring large two-dimensional matrices of high-dimensional semantic embedding vectors, which were noted as part of demonstrator development. We demonstrate that in the admittedly favorable circumstances the system was tested under, embedding quantization produces very little observable variation in object retrieval.

2. Background

2.1. Conventions

The conventions used in this article mainly have to do with the representations of robot poses $T = (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{t}) \in \text{SE3}$. While the translation vector $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is treated the same everywhere, two redundant parametrizations of rotation \mathbf{r} are used—quaternions and rotation matrices. In the LLP context, due to middleware conventions, poses are treated as tuples

$$T = (\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{t}) : \mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{H}, |\mathbf{q}| = 1 \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{q} is a unit quaternion representing rotation. In the perception system context, due to the need to work with camera projection matrices, the pose matrix

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} R & \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4} : R \in \text{SO3} \quad (2)$$

is used instead, with R denoting a rotation matrix in the special orthogonal group SO3 .

2.2. Motion Planning with Action Primitives

Action primitives are an architectural approach proposed for dealing with the complexity of manually implementing functionality for the many permutations of a task an autonomous robotic system may encounter. These involve the use of procedures in a generalized form, which can be adapted to different scenarios. Depending on whether the implementations abstract only motions or different robot functions, they may be referred to in the literature as dynamic motion primitives [6], action primitives [7], or robot skills [8].

Action primitives and actions, the abstractions used in this work, model each possible functionality of the robot as a behavior, which can be induced by higher-level control, a perceived event, or another behavior [9]. This behavior-based control is made up of individual behaviors that can function independently [10]. Action primitives can often be

encountered in robotic systems that can perform variations of certain base tasks. A variety of actions can be performed by chaining together primitives, or composite actions made up of multiple primitives. For example in [11] a set of action primitives is available for different assembly and kitting tasks. Similarly, in [4,12] a set of action primitives is made available for the system that is recognized as a skill set. When given a task, a plan of available primitives is made to complete it, which is then executed.

2.3. High-Level Planning with LLMs

The ability to parse arbitrary natural language commands is a crucial milestone to achieve before robots can be expected to safely and easily collaborate with people—especially people other than specially trained operators—in unstructured environments. LLMs have recently made great advances in natural language understanding, which has contributed to a large number of works attempting to leverage their use in robotics [13,14]. While some work such as *DeepMind's RT2* [5] explores the use of transformer models to directly generate motion commands for the robot—in effect subsuming a large part of the traditional planning and control stack—this makes integration with discrete, structure environment representations and pre-existing industrial motion control stacks more complex, and necessitates training multi-modal models directly on robotics tasks. An alternative approach is that of a separate high-level planning (HLP) to produce a sequence of commands for a lower-level planning and control stack. When it comes to HLP, there are several ways an LLM can be integrated into the planning process.

The first approach is end-to-end plan generation as in LLM-Planner [15]. Information about the scene is received during execution and replanning is performed to accommodate the current state of the environment as required. A somewhat similar approach is shown in Text2Motion [16]—the plan is generated in full, then evaluated action by action to determine feasibility and replanned if necessary. Rather than generating the full plan, SayCan [4] uses an LLM to score a set of skills based on their likelihood to complete the given task, combined with a similar evaluation of the current visual scene to calculate the final decision, and does so action by action. On the other hand, LLM+P [17] is a method skeptical of LLMs' ability to perform true planning, rather putting focus on its natural language processing ability to create a PDDL description which then is passed onto a traditional planner.

As highlighted in [13], many of these methods rely on large, service-based models, which, while showcasing superior results to the smaller LLMs [18], require much larger compute resources and, if provided as a service, a constant connection to the internet. Few works focus on using a smaller LLM as the main NLP and planning mechanism, but one such implementation can be seen with LLaRP [19], where the 7 billion parameter LLaMA [20] model is modified to also take visual observations and output actions, where reinforcement learning is used to train the action output module while the LLM remains frozen. The use of smaller LLMs can allow placing these systems closer to the actual robot performing the tasks and improve its practical autonomy.

2.4. Open-Set Image Segmentation and Semantic Mapping

Open-set semantics are a novel direction in perception enabled by the shared representation of textual and visual concepts in a single vector space by VLMs [21]. Where traditional image segmentation maps each pixel in the image plane to a discrete probability distribution over a finite set of semantic categories [22], open-set segmentation performs a regression in the shared language–visual embeddings vector space, where visual features and textual descriptions corresponding to them map to similar vectors. The open-set segmentation approach in this paper, shown in Figure 1, is based on *Conceptfusion* [23], which introduced an open-set image segmentation algorithm alongside a method for integrating its outputs into a spatially consistent semantic map.

Figure 1. An open-set segmentation of a scene (**left**) colored by similarity to the queries *scissors* (**center**) and *computer mouse* (**right**).

For depth or range scan observations into a spatial model of the environment, the three most common approaches are point- or surfel-clouds, grid maps, and implicit functions. The first category typically uses methods similar to *Point-based fusion* [24] to produce unstructured lists of points that may also contain radius and normal information for surface reconstruction. While effective at generating high-fidelity visual reconstructions of scenes, every sensor insertion, render or spatial query operation requires a linear pass over the full list of surfels, imposing a considerable performance overhead. Gridmaps partition the working volume into evenly spaced elements with associated occupancy probabilities and additional information such as color [25]. This is often paired with a space partitioning binary tree data structure—a quadtree for 2-dimensional maps and an octree for 3-dimensional ones—to vastly reduce computational space requirements by not instantiating nodes containing free space, as in *Octomap* [26]. Assuming constant tree-depth, an octree gridmap offers constant time spatial queries (with compounding effects for path planning and raycasting), predictable bounds on space requirements, and inherent multi-resolution capabilities. The final broad class of common spatial representation methods could be described as implicit function fields, ranging from gridmap-like structures such as truncated signed distance fields (TSDF) [27] to neural radiance fields [28,29], which require that a parametric function be evaluated at any given coordinate input to perform a lookup operation.

With the exception of neural radiance fields, where it is simply a learned distribution over the position inputs, most of these data structures have provisions to store color in vector form. Sensor updates may then involve performing a weighted vector averaging of existing color values with new observations. The same method has been extended to semantics—for example, the fundamental approach of *Point-based fusion* was first extended to discrete semantic segmentation by *Semanticfusion* [30], before serving as the basis for the spatial mapping component of *Conceptfusion*.

3. Proposed Approach

When drafting a system architecture, it is important to first define the use-case and user interaction scenario. In this case, we constrain the scenario to feature the human operator of a workstation overseeing the robot control system issuing commands in natural language. This inherently couples the user interaction with other low-level control elements of the system, and we therefore place the LLP application at the core of the architecture. Action primitives are hosted as action servers, performing a parameterized motion when called. The HLP, image segmentation, text embedding, and map components of the system are deployed separately, to decouple their computational constraints from each other and the robot control system

hardware. The system, a schematic of which is presented in Figure 2, executes the following event loop, driven by the main application which is integrated with the LLP:

1. The user inputs a text prompt using the command line UI (Figure 2, top left), which is passed to the planner client.
2. The HLP (deployed on a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster) is called by the planner client with the input text. It returns a plan descriptor, composed of a list of action descriptors, each of which contains unpopulated object descriptors. This plan is passed down to the action sequencer.
3. For each unpopulated object descriptor in the plan, the language embedding server is called to produce latent space embeddings—query vectors—corresponding to the textual descriptions of the objects.
4. For each object that requires a centroid or grasp pose estimate, the corresponding map API—find or grasp—is called with the query vector to retrieve relevant spatial information and populate the object descriptor.
5. Once the object descriptors are populated, each action descriptor is passed to the corresponding primitive action server (bottom right).

Figure 2. Architecture of the system demonstrator.

4. Implementation

Practical implementation of the approach above necessitates the development of multiple distinct subsystems and the communication interfaces between them. The LLP, with its action sequencer and primitives, are tightly coupled to the robot control system, and therefore heavily rely on ROS 2 [31] for inter-process communication and motion planning-related utilities. As the HLP and language embedder heavily rely on LLMs, they have been decoupled from the ROS 2 system through HTTP-based REST APIs for

simplifying remote deployment. The two mapping systems—the direct depth image segmentation and the 3-dimensional map—are each deployed in a separate software package, interfacing with the rest of the system over REST or ROS APIs.

4.1. High-Level Planning

The main goal of high-level planning in this application is to transform an incoming user request, stated in natural language, into an action plan that the rest of the system can act upon. The plan is made through successive calls to the LLM that progressively populate prompt templates with information extracted from the user query. In this system, we use the following:

- The LLama3 8B Instruct [32] model—an instruction fine-tuned LLM in the 8 billion parameter size range;
- The Q_4K_M weights available at [33];
- Four-bit GGUF quantization implemented by *llama.cpp* [34]—to reduce the model’s memory footprint.

We use prompt chaining [35] to also reduce context length requirements. This also allows for additional programmatic post-processing of the output text between LLM calls. The HLP module processes inputs through the following stages: filtration, parsing, and planning. All stages utilize few-shot prompting [36], where each prompt contains examples for the task at hand.

In filtration, incoming requests are classified into one of the predefined classes—“*mobile_manipulation*”, “*query_answering*”, “*casual_discussion*” and “*any_other_query*”. This is used to trigger different execution paths in the following stages. Currently, only “*mobile_manipulation*” is implemented, with other types of request terminating the high-level planning sequence. Filtration is achieved by invoking the model with the instruction prompt in Listing 1.

Listing 1. Filtration prompt.

```
You are a natural language interpreter.
You can classify incoming requests under one of the predefined categories.
The categories that you can classify sentences are:
"object_manipulation", 1 - requests concerning finding, moving, placing objects;
"query_answering", 2 - requests that need knowledge to be answered;
"casual_discussion", 3 - requests that are expecting a human response.
"Any_Other_Query", 0 - for requests that can not be placed under the other 3

Example of the format that you answer in:
Input: What a lovely day it is, isn't it?
Category: ["casual_discussion", 3]
```

The parsing stage first identifies relevant objects and locations which would need to be found in the environment for the system to perform its task. It then breaks down the request into simpler sub-tasks (referred to as “Steps”) for which planning can be performed separately, as in the Least-to-Most [37] approach. The object description consists of a placeholder, a textual description, and an object ID unique in the scope of the entire plan. An example of the JSON output format is given in Listing 2.

Listing 2. JSON format for plan descriptors.

```
Input: On the small block, place the large box
Output:
{  "Query": "On the small block, place the large box"
   "Objects": [ ["<small_block>", "small block", 0], ["<large_box>", "large box",
               1] ],
   "Steps": [ ["Pick up <large_box>", [1]], ["Place <large_box> on <small_block>",
               [0]] ]
}
```

The final stage is the actual planning—sequencing of actions. Each step created during “parsing” is processed by the planning stage as a list of actions from the available skill set, defined by the available action primitives. Chain-of-Thought (CoT) [38] prompting, which instructs the model to generate additional information before the final answer, is used to improve planning consistency and quality. To maintain continuity between steps, the expected state of the gripper (empty or holding an object) is generated as part of the output and passed as an input for the next step’s planning operation. For example, the request in Listing 3 may produce an output such as the intermediate result in Listing 4.

Listing 3. Planning request.

```
Request: "Place the <big_fish> on the <small_plate>"
```

Listing 4. Intermediate state prompt.

```
Objects: [{"<big_fish>", "big fish", 3}, {"<small_plate>", "small plate", 4}]
Hand: ["empty"]
Interpretation:
My Hand: Free
My hand is Free and I need to pick up the <big_fish> and place it on the <
  small_plate>. I will:
1. Pick <big_fish>. my Hand: <big_fish>
2. Place the <big_fish> on the <small_plate>. my Hand: empty
No more actions needed.

Plan:
{
  "Actions": [[1, "Pick", [3]], [2, "Place", [4]]],
  "Hand": ["empty"],
  "Misc": None
}
```

These sub-task plans are concatenated to create the full plan, a container of action descriptors, which themselves may contain multiple object descriptors. This is then passed on to the LLP.

4.2. Low-Level Planning

Low-level planning (LLP) is responsible for planning and controlling the execution of each step in the plan provided by the HLP subsystem on physical hardware. It is tightly coupled to the low-level control aspects of the robot system and therefore developed within the ROS 2 framework for inter-process communication and task scheduling, with the corresponding version of *MoveIt* [39] employed for motion planning and control.

A set of five action primitives is defined following the action–activity hierarchy defined in [40]: **embed**, **find**, **get_grasp**, **move** and **activate_gripper**. These action primitives can be divided into subgroups such as for perception, consisting of **embed**, **find**, **get_grasp** and for robot motion, which includes **move** and **activate_gripper**.

The **perception primitives** are defined as ROS 2 service calls that wrap REST API calls for communicating with external components. The client side is directly embedded in the LLP software module as a function or method call, while the server node handles the REST API calls. The perception primitives may be viewed as functions:

- **embed**: $\text{string} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{\text{semantic_dim}}$ —wraps a call to the VLM text embedder API, returns the latent space embedding of the input text;
- **find**: $\mathbb{R}^{\text{semantic_dim}} \mapsto \text{Option}[\mathbb{R}^3]$ —wraps a map API call with an embedded object descriptor string, and converts the camera-frame position \mathbf{t}^C to base-frame position \mathbf{t}^B (may return empty when no object found);
- **get_grasp**: $\mathbb{R}^{\text{semantic_dim}} \mapsto \text{Option}[\text{SE3}]$ —returns the base-frame grasp pose T_{grasp}^B for an object described by the embedding vector (may return empty when no object found).

The **robot motion primitives** abstract robot operation. Currently only two of these are implemented—sufficient for simple pick-and-place operations required by the minimal proof-of-concept architecture:

- **move**: $SE3 \mapsto \text{bool}$ —wraps planning and execution calls through *MoveIt*, potentially using a mix of joint-space and Cartesian paths depending on the goal and current state of the robot, returns a flag indicating whether the trajectory was completed successfully;
- **activate_gripper**: $\text{bool} \mapsto \text{bool}$ —wraps calls to a ROS action server that open or close the gripper, returns a flag indicating whether the target gripper state was achieved.

The primitives are treated as composable subroutines to form **actions**. Two actions have been implemented in this system—**pick** and **place**. Each is defined as a procedure that invokes the primitives as subroutines, depicted in Figure 3. These actions define the skill set of the system, and plans created by the HLP are expressed as sequences of these actions.

Figure 3. Pick (I) and place (II) action flowcharts.

A communication interface consistent with all actions implemented by the LLP system is implemented in the form of two ROS message types:

- **ActionDesc**—the argument for each action call
 - *sequence id* : int
 - *action type* : string
 - *objects* : list[ObjDesc]
- **ObjDesc**
 - *text description* : string
 - *latent description* : Option[$\mathbb{R}^{\text{semantic_dim}}$]
 - *object position* : Option[\mathbb{R}^3]
 - *grasp pose* : Option[SE3]

Fields of an optional type are populated by the perception primitives if and when required.

The LLP module is directly integrated with the main execution loop and user interface of the system. Therefore, HLP requests are made by the LLP code through a middleman ROS service which abstracts the external HLP interface. This returns a sequence of **ActionDesc** objects. These are iterated over in sequence order, and the action type string is used to select the corresponding action to invoke with each.

4.3. Perception

To enable interoperability between the high-level planner and low-level action primitives, a perception system capable of associating natural language concepts with the concrete geometry of the robot’s work environment is required. Open-set image segmentation was selected as the primary perception method, and queryable map representations were developed to integrate and serve observations thus processed for use by other parts of the system.

4.3.1. Open-Set Image Segmentation

The basis for image segmentation is the method used by ConceptFusion [23]. The Segment Anything Model (SAM) [41] used in the original system has been substituted with FastSAM [42] to reduce the otherwise prohibitive inference times on available hardware. This is a two stage approach: first, the segmentation model generates a set of masks that ideally correspond to objects of interest in the scene. Then, the image as a whole and cropped regions around each mask are passed through the OpenCLIP [43] image embedder, creating a single latent space embedding associated with each mask. The final semantic segmentation is created by summing over the embeddings of every mask covering each pixel. All of these operations are by default performed at 32-bit floating point precision, setting this as the upper bound for information content in any downstream consumer of these images. While this system obtains high-quality results, its multiple-pass nature presents as significant performance bottleneck, necessitating exploration into alternatives for future iterations of the pipeline.

4.3.2. Environment Modeling

To populate the object descriptions in the plans produced by the HLP, an environment modeling system capable of extracting discrete object information from regions of semantically annotated space is required. Two such environment representations were developed—an interim 2.5D solution consisting of a simple depth map, sufficient for modeling small static scenes from a fixed vantage point, as well as a fully 3-dimensional occupancy map capable of integrating many depth images or laser scans taken from multiple vantage points, and semantically annotating the resulting points with image segmentations.

The 2.5D semantic depthmap is obtained by associating a depth value with each pixel in the segmented image. When using most depth cameras, this may involve the additional step of registering the depth image in the RGB image reference frame. However, in cases where an already-aligned depth channel is available, this is essentially “free”. For this demonstrator, a fixed *Zivid One+* depth camera was used, which provides a registered depth image. To turn this into a map of the robot’s environment, an extrinsic calibration to the workspace coordinate frame and the camera’s intrinsic parameters are required (see Section 5.1), enabling conversion between the depth values and point coordinates in \mathbb{R}^3 .

The fully 3-dimensional semantic map is based on the the **vectree**—an octree occupancy grid map with vector-valued nodes, shown in Figure 4 (II). As the reconstruction of high-fidelity visual images is not a priority, this data structure was selected due to the simplicity of its associated search, retrieval and integration operations. We use the octree implementation in *Octomap* [26], extended with our *VectorOcTreeNode* and *VectorOcTree* data structures templated by node vector dimension.

To avoid unnecessary memory allocation and access overhead, as well as to decouple the arithmetic type of the vector from its storage properties, we also provide an abstracted *VectorStore* data structure, which holds a *unique_ptr* to a vector. After initial experiments revealed that a full precision floating point number does not have to be stored for acceptable recall, versions storing the embeddings as fixed point 8-bit integers and ternary values packed 5 *trits* to a byte were implemented. Currently, to maintain compatibility with past and future experiments, tree storage, vector integration, and dot product comparison operations are implemented in 64-bit floating point precision, meaning that the quantized representations need to be expanded for arithmetic or filesystem I/O operations.

The vectree is designed to accept point clouds pre-aligned with the map reference frame by an external pose estimation system (approximated here by mounting the sensor on the robot and using a known calibration), alongside segmented images with a known transformation matrix to the scan point of origin. The raycast-based update method is inherited directly from *Octomap*, with the only notable addition being the fact that, during the update step, updated points which fall inside the segmentation field of view also have their vector values updated. If a point is previously unseen, its *VectorStore* allocates a new vector with the observed value; otherwise, a weighted averaging between

the new and old values is performed. For this demonstrator the following averaging scheme, inherited directly from *ColorOcTree*, was found to be adequate:

$$\mathbf{v}_{t+1}(\mathbf{x}) = o_t(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{v}_t(\mathbf{x}) + (1 - o_t(\mathbf{x}))\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (3)$$

where at time step t and spatial coordinate \mathbf{x} , $\mathbf{v}_t(\mathbf{x})$, $o_t(\mathbf{x})$ are the embedding vector and occupancy value, while $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})$ is the novel observation to be integrated.

Figure 4. A scene in the reference data set (see Section 5.2) (I) Image of the scene. (II) Vector octree map reconstruction at a resolution of 0.01 m, colored by similarity to the query “scotch tape”, with a grasp pose estimate indicated by a shifted coordinate axes markers. (III) Manually annotated reference grasps. Center (red cross) and direction (blue asterisk) indicators drawn as seen by the user of the data set tagging utility. (IV) A visualization showing a semantic map grasp pose estimate and the corresponding ground-truth annotation.

4.3.3. Object Detection and Grasp Pose Estimation

For direct grasp inference on RGB-D data (the 2.5d case), the system relies on GG-CNN [44], a direct RGB-D to grasp model, as this was found to offer a good compromise between grasp quality, performance on available hardware and ease of integration. The demonstrator estimates the grasp pose once before executing a grasping attempt. After the desired object in the scene is identified through the text query, a 400-by-400 bounding box is created around the highlighted region. The corresponding region is cropped out of the depth image and passed to GG-CNN (GG-CNN requires a 300-by-300 image, so it

is scaled down). The model returns the grasping pose estimation at the most promising point. The point's coordinates are converted from pixel-based to metric in the robot frame of reference and passed to the robot controller for execution. Because the depth map may contain "NaN" (not a number) values, the system can find the nearest non-NaN value to take as the grasping point instead.

With the 3D voxel map the general approach for finding objects using a latent space embedding consists of three steps:

1. A filtered point cloud at the desired resolution is obtained by iterating over the vectree nodes and rejecting points based on a dot product similarity threshold with the query embedding;
2. Clusters are found in the filtered pointcloud using *DBScan* [45] with manually tuned parameters;
3. Cluster parameters such as the centroid, object-aligned bounding box, point count, etc., are computed and used for scoring.

Tunable parameters include the nonlinearities (currently, the dot products are normalized to the range $[0, 1]$ and raised to some even power) and thresholding applied to the dot product similarity metric; the *DBScan* parameters ϵ and *min_points*; bounding box size, centroid placement, point count constraints for rejection of invalid clusters. While fully general 6DoF grasp pose estimation is a complex task necessitating involved machine learning-based approaches [46], the use case selected for this demonstrator allows for significant simplifying assumptions and therefore enables the direct use of outputs from the object finding algorithm for grasp estimation. Namely, all objects are assumed to have bounding boxes that are graspable by the robot gripper, and all grasps are assumed to be vertical. The grasp pose $T_{grasp} = (R, \mathbf{t})$ is obtained by first setting the grasp position \mathbf{t} as equal to the bounding box center. Then, for obtaining the rotation, the longest oriented axis projection on the workspace XY plane is identified as

$$\mathbf{p} = \max_{i \in \{x,y,z\}} \left\| \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} * R_{bbox} * \mathbf{e}_i \right\| = \begin{bmatrix} p_x \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z$ —bounding box extent vectors along each axis and R_{bbox} —the oriented bounding box rotation matrix. By the convention used, the gripper actuation direction is the tool frame x axis, meaning the corresponding rotation matrix is given by

$$\theta = \arctan 2 \left(\frac{p_y}{p_x} \right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$R_{grasp} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The system described in Section 4 was deployed in a real-world laboratory test environment for verifying end-to-end execution capability and performing tests of the environment representation modules.

5. Experimental Setup and Results

In accordance with the stated goal of this article—demonstrating the novel LLM, open-set map, and action primitive stack at a proof-of-concept level—we have conducted three types of experimental validation and verification. Firstly, we perform end-to-end execution on real hardware, to validate the fundamental viability of our approach. Second, we perform recall tests in the semantic map, to verify its capacity to serve as an object detection and grasp pose estimation pipeline, and compare the effects of different quantization approaches. Finally, we test the ability of the HLP to successfully reconstruct plans when presented with variously permuted natural language commands generated from them.

5.1. Evaluation Environment

All real-world data were collected in the same workspace, featuring a *Universal Robots UR5e* manipulator equipped with a *RobotiQ* finger-type gripper; a static *Zivid One+* RGB-D camera for the static 2.5D segmentation; a robot-mounted *Intel Realsense D435* depth camera for testing the integration of observations from multiple known vantage points into a single vectree map; a flat working surface on which various objects were placed for identification and manipulation. End-to-end execution of a system event loop was accomplished as part of integration testing, seen in Figure 5. The *ZividOne+* camera was calibrated using the manufacturer’s proprietary toolkit. With the *Realsense*, intrinsic parameters broadcast by the device’s ROS driver and eye-in-hand extrinsic calibration obtained with [47] were used. The camera poses used in building the 3-dimensional map were thus obtained as

$$T_c^w = T_{tcp}^w (T_{tcp}^c)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where T_c^w is the world frame camera pose, T_{tcp}^w is the robot tool center point (tcp) pose measured when capturing an image and T_{tcp}^c is the extrinsic eye-in-hand calibration, which is fixed.

Figure 5. End-to-end execution on the real robot. Given the command “put the toy car on the realsense box”, the HLP produces a sequence containing a pick action (I,II) followed by a place action (III), which the LLP decomposes into primitives and executes. Object poses obtained from the vectree map.

5.2. Reference Scene Data Set

To obtain a means of systematically evaluating system performance between design iterations, a data set of several reference scenes was collected, shown in Figure 4 as items (III) and (IV). A tool for human operators to annotate images with object centroids, textual queries describing them and (potentially multiple) valid grasp directions was developed. The center points were associated with reprojected depth points, while the directions were projected onto the workspace coordinate frame XY plane. This way, a set of object center points and 4-DoF (vertically fixed) grasp poses is obtained, though the latter can only be expected to approximate the grasp distribution generated by the vectree map as the GGCNN is not constrained by object centroids or verticality. Five configurations of the scene were set up, observed with both depth cameras and annotated in this fashion. Additional camera pose information was also captured to enable creation of 3-dimensional maps.

5.3. Embedding Quantization

Using open-set semantics imposes a considerable computational space overhead, which grows quadratically with size in planar images and cubically—in volumetric representations

of space. For example, an uncompressed 480×640 image containing 768-dimensional embeddings in 64-bit precision takes up approx. 1.9 GB of memory or storage space. Considering the discrete mask-based method of generating the segmented images in *Conceptfusion*, the actual information content in the images is far lower—with sizes on the order of 10–30 MB obtained by lossless *zlib* compression [48] depending on the settings used. For this reason, in our systems segmented images are compressed before being sent over HTTP or stored on disk. However, stream compression methods are impractical for random access operations due to their non-locality. For this reason, experiments were conducted with pixel and voxel embeddings stored at various precision levels—the original 32-bit floating point precision of the image segmentation model, 8-bit fixed point and ternary.

The center point annotations available in the reference scene data set can be used to verify that the correct object was retrieved with both perception systems, even though the grasp comparison is only valid for the vectree. Specifically, if any object corresponding to the query is returned, the XY-plane projection of its position and the centroid given by the label data is compared. If within a tolerance of 5 cm, the map is considered to have recalled the correct object.

The results of this test are recorded in Table 1. Each row in the table corresponds to an object query—which is also a unique object in the reference scene data set. The rightmost column indicates the number of times this object is present in the reference scenes. A model of each reference scene was constructed and a search was conducted for each of the objects marked as present in the annotation data. The “Recall %” columns indicate the fraction of these search attempts that retrieved the correct object.

Table 1. Object queries and recall rates according to map type and vector quantization level.

Query Text	Recall %						Seen # Times
	Static Depth Map			VectorOcTree Map			
	Ternary	Byte	Float32	Ternary	Byte	Float32	
protective eyewear	75.00	100.00	75.00	75.00	75.00	75.00	4
pink foam	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.67	66.67	3
grey key	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	1
realsense box	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	2
wrench	100.00	40.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	5
computer mouse	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	5
white bottle	60.00	60.00	60.00	40.00	60.00	60.00	5
multimeter	100.00	66.67	66.67	100.00	100.00	100.00	3
blue stapler	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	3
toy car	80.00	60.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	5
red lego	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	3
scotch tape	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	5
pair of scissors	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	4
energy drink bottle	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.67	100.00	100.00	3
tape measure	100.00	75.00	100.00	75.00	75.00	75.00	4
blue lego	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	1
Mean recall	94.69	87.60	93.85	91.04	92.29	92.29	$\Sigma = 56$

5.4. HLP Performance

Position the energy drink bottle over the toy car, then rest the pair of scissors on the multimeter. While the above tests give some indication of semantic map performance, they give no insight into the ability of the HLP to reliably decompose commands into action sequences. One way to verify such a system is to start with known plans, construct commands from them and test whether the HLP is able to recover the original plan. As the current system is limited to a very simple set of actions, the following three types of command were selected to test for different potential failure modes:

- “simple”—simple verb–object statements, corresponding to a single “pick” → “place” action sequence, to test for robustness in wording;
- “forward”—composite statements of multiple (in this case, two) simple pick–place sequences, to test for the model’s ability to correctly isolate actions from each other;
- “reverse”—composite statements reversed sentence order, e.g., “do B, but only after doing A”, to test the model’s ability to recover correct sequencing.

Due to the absence of an existing data set, a method for collecting such commands is necessary. LLMs, by construction, approximate the distribution of natural language sequences quite well. However, using the same model as in the HLP would result in test sequences reflecting the same biases. To minimize the chances of encountering such effects, it was decided to sample statements using a different large language model. In this case, the interactive assistant API of *OpenAI’s* flagship *GPT-4o* [49] was used.

Specifically, generating the test sequences was accomplished by following the prompt chain in Listing 5, where the previous prompt and the resulting model output are included in the context of the subsequent model invocation along with the new prompt. To further obfuscate the required actions, we also take an additional step to make each command resemble more typical human conversation by continuing the process with the prompts in Listing 6.

Listing 5. Prompt chain for generating the “dry” sequences.

```
Step 1: Generate 20 different ways to say "pick up object A and put it down on
object B". Put each variation in a new line preceded by its index. Use creative
wording but keep the meaning the same.
---
Step 2: Produce a shortened version of each, e.g.
"pick up object A and put it down on object B" -> "put object A on object B"
---
Step 3: For each pair i, i+1, write a way to combine the statements:
"Put object A on object B. Then, set object C on object D."
finish by looping back around.
---
Step 4: create a version of each line where C and D are mentioned before A and B,
but the action with A and B is still to be performed first, e.g.
"Put object C on object D, but only after aligning object A with object B"
```

Listing 6. Prompt chain for generating the “extended” sequences.

```
Step 5: look at the simple commands in the output of step 2 (shortened versions)
and make them into natural sentences where a boss is telling his employee to do
something. Use different phrases as much as possible.
---
Step 6: Do the same thing with the two-step commands from step 3
---
Step 7: do the same with the reverse-order two-step commands from step 4
```

This results in a total of 120 templates. An example of each type is given in Listing 7.

Listing 7. Variations of a command by structure and style.

```
# simple, dry
Situating object A over object B.
# simple, extended
Please situate object A over object B.
# forward, dry
Situating object A over object B, then placing down object C on object D.
# forward, extended
Please situate object A over object B first, and then place down object C on
object D.
# reverse, dry
```

Place down object C on object D, but only after situating object A over object B.
 # reverse, extended
 Please place down object C on object D, but only after situating object A over object B.

To fill the templates, combinations of unique objects from the reference scene data set were used (see Table 1, the query text column). To make it possible to detect cases of object duplication or incorrect ordering, only non-repeating combinations are used. Since both the **pick** and **place** actions only feature a single object each, each filled template induces a plan signature in the form of

$$\sigma = (\alpha, \omega) = ((a_1, \dots, a_k), (o_1, \dots, o_k)) \quad (8)$$

where a_i, o_i are the i -th action and object identifier respectively in a list of k actions. These can be compared with the corresponding fields in a sequence of action descriptors returned by the HLP. It must be noted that, in principle, the LLM could still produce a correct plan by substituting o_i or a_i with a synonym, making a direct equality comparison invalid. In practice the only alterations that have been observed are in object capitalization, so we perform conversion to lowercase. However, human inspection of incorrect signatures is still ultimately required to verify the absence of false negatives. We distinguish between three types of failures:

1. planning failure—the HLP is unable to construct a plan and returns an error;
2. structural failure—a plan is returned, but does not match the sequence of actions a_i ;
3. object failure—a plan is returned and matches the action sequence, but not all of the objects o_i have been correctly identified.

Formally, we deterministically sample $n = 200$ reference object signatures ω_i^r from the space of $P(16, 4) = 43,680$ possible object set permutations. For each object signature ω_i^r , we iterate over all of the possible command types τ and construct a reference plan signature by prepending the action signature $\alpha_i^r(\tau)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &\in \{\text{simple, forward, reverse}\} \times \{\text{dry, extended}\} \\ \sigma_i^r(\tau) &= (\alpha_i^r(\tau), \omega_i^r) = ((a_1^r(\tau), \dots, a_k^r(\tau)), (o_1^r, \dots, o_k^r)) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Permutations that differ only in their object C and D produce identical signatures for the *simple* command type—we discard duplicates. Next, for each of the constructed plan signatures we sample a template index $\eta \in \{1, \dots, 20\}$, construct the query $s_i(\tau)$ and call the HLP to yield a plan p_i and planning error flag ϵ_p

$$\begin{aligned} s_i(\tau) &= \text{fill_template}(\tau, \eta) \\ \epsilon_p, p(\tau) &= \text{HLP}(s(\tau)) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

which is compared to the reference signature $\sigma_i^r(\tau)$ to yield the structural and object error

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i^p(\tau) \neq \alpha_i^r(\tau) &\rightarrow \epsilon_s \\ \omega_i^p(\tau) \neq \omega_i^r(\tau) &\rightarrow \epsilon_o \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

and the planning result is classified by the leftmost error type in the order $\epsilon_p, \epsilon_s, \epsilon_o$.

$$\text{error type} = \begin{cases} \text{planning, if } \epsilon_p \\ \text{structure, if } \neg\epsilon_p \wedge \epsilon_s \\ \text{object, if } \neg\epsilon_p \wedge \neg\epsilon_s \wedge \epsilon_o \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

This means that the total used to compute the percentage in the “object” column of the table only counts instances without planning or structural errors, and “structure”—only

the instances without planning errors. We collect the $\tau, p_i(\tau)$ sequence, its corresponding text queries and error flags into files, which have been included in the *hlp_results.zip* archive of the reference data set cited in the data availability statement at the end of this article. Also included are files in which only the lines corresponding to a specific error type and query type are collected.

The results of this comparison are collected in Table 2. The rows correspond to command structure, the two major column blocks—to whether the dry or extended version of the command is being tested. Each column then records the frequency of a particular error type given a command type. The rightmost row records the bottom line—the percentage of correctly recovered plans across both styles of language. The bottom row combines the results across all command types.

Table 2. HLP performance by command type.

Command Type	Dry				Extended				Correct %
	Error % by Type (of Total)								
	Planning	Structure	Object	Any	Planning	Structure	Object	Any	
simple	00.00	0.51	00.00	0.51	0.00	0.51	0.00	0.51	99.49
forward	1.50	1.50	1.50	4.50	3.50	6.00	1.00	10.50	92.50
reverse	1.00	0.50	0.50	2.00	2.00	1.00	0.50	3.50	97.25
all	0.84	0.84	0.67	2.35	1.84	2.51	0.50	4.86	96.40
Data set size									
Command type	Dry				Extended				Total
simple	197				197				394
forward	200				200				400
reverse	200				200				400
all	597				597				1194

6. Discussion

Given a sufficiently constrained scenario—pick-and-place operations on a flat surface within the robot’s field of view and reach—it is clear, as evidenced by the successful end-to-end execution in Figure 5, that it is indeed possible to implement a natural language-based robot control system following the approach outlined in this article, which answers the main question outlined by the authors at the start of this article.

Examining the results of the HLP performance evaluation, it is clear that, at least for the three simple types of plans presented in the test data set, adequate performance is attainable with the methods used. However, as is seen in Table 2, a counter-intuitive result can be observed—in that the error rates in the forward version of the composite query are higher than those in the reverse. Closer examination of the corresponding files in the reference data set seems to show a pattern where additional actions are hallucinated as in Listing 8 or objects are duplicated as in Listing 9.

Listing 8. Error due to hallucinated actions.

```
# hlp_results/dry/eval_forward_err_struct.txt - 1
# query
Set the goggles on the grey key, then position the toy car over the white bottle.
# plan
['pick', 'place', 'pick', 'place', 'place']
# objects
['goggles', 'grey key', 'toy car', 'white bottle', 'toy car']
```

Listing 9. Error due to duplicated objects.

```
# hlp_results/dry/eval_forward_err_obj.txt - 1
# query
Position the energy drink bottle over the toy car, then rest the pair of scissors
on the multimeter.
# plan
['pick', 'place', 'pick', 'place']
# objects
['energy drink bottle', 'energy drink bottle', 'pair of scissors', 'multimeter']
```

Curiously, this happens in the forward case more frequently than in the reverse case, and is only exacerbated by the use of less straightforward language (as in the extended query set). The extended queries also result in higher rates of false negative classification—prompts that are worded as questions are more likely to be rejected by the planner as not relevant. This is reflected in the results table as an increase in the planning error. Extending the alphabet of available actions in the robot’s skill set will inevitably dramatically increase the number of permutations in their sequences, and proportionally expand the space of possible plans, complicating the task of selecting a correct one. Furthermore, scene complexity may confound intuiting the roles to be played by different objects and selecting between them. The current approaches used to detect objects have no real way to differentiate between objects of the same type by contextual cues—such as proximity of relative placement—as the model performing object identification in the command has no way to perceive the layout of the scene, and relies entirely on the context available in the command itself. In its current form, the HLP has no priors regarding the state of its surroundings and no way to keep track of dependencies between multiple invocations, an issue of critical importance to be addressed in further work. This may be mitigated by including observations of the environment in the HLP models’ context—either directly by making the model multi-modal, as is conducted in *RT2* [5], or by using a separate model, such as a VLM, to provide textual descriptions of the scene. As is, the system may be capable of dealing with some simple industrial manipulation tasks, but not at a level of complexity where the advantages of open-ended NLP-based planning outweigh the costs paid in terms of computational overhead and determinism.

Other potential complications may arise in perceiving complex scenes—the object detection methods employed by the mapping systems are not robust to objects that are not cleanly separable. As scenes grow more cluttered, this may result in merged objects or undue rejections. An obvious improvement to be made in the 2.5d case would be the adoption of point-based *DBSCAN* [45] clustering, which is already used in the vectree, to help merge overlapping masks of the same object and result in more stable segmentations over multiple observations of the same scene. To help deal with objects that are not separable at the voxel resolution, integrating another, different clustering step, such as *k-means* [50], may be necessary.

A potential upside alluded to, though far from decisively confirmed due to the small size of the experimental data set, is that significant reductions in embedding vector scalar precision may be permissible with minimal reduction in real-world recall. This potentially opens the way to major performance optimization in future iterations of the system, accelerating prospects of practical adoption in real-world use cases. While this data set, with 56 total object observations, is too small to draw any valid statistical conclusions, no clear trend is immediately apparent. For the static depth map, using ternary embedding values appears to paradoxically result in slightly improved recall—though this peculiarity is likely to disappear with larger and more varied data sets. With the vectree map, the same output set was produced by 32-bit and 8-bit embeddings, with two otherwise recalled observations being missed (one each of “*white bottle*” and “*energy drink bottle*”) and one otherwise missed observation being recalled (“*pink foam*”). A fortunate byproduct of the work performed in testing for the effects of quantization is the development of the partially automated data

labeling system. This can further be used to produce larger, more statistically useful data sets, for more extensive quantitative validation during subsequent iterations of this system.

7. Conclusions

The primary goal established at the outset—demonstrating the viability of the conceptual architecture proposed in Section 3—has been accomplished. Given a sufficiently constrained space of tasks—two or four action pick-and-place sequences, and a sufficiently constrained space of observations—a static tabletop scene, planning success and object recall rates in excess of 90% are observed. However, even the limited tabletop manipulation use-case—with a fixed robot arm—calls for a larger set of actions in the available skill set before clear advantages of processing free-form natural language commands over a simple finite set of “buttons to be clicked” becomes apparent. The counter-intuitive results observed when testing the responses of the HLP to permuted commands in different forms also reinforce the point that LLMs do not think like humans do, and overly generalizing conclusions drawn from small data sets is not advisable. Tackling less constrained environments will inevitably challenge many simplifying assumptions made during the implementation of the HLP and semantic maps. For the HLP, dealing with mobile manipulation and multi-agent systems may significantly compound the issues relating to structuring and parsing the output data, with potential multi-layered hierarchical relationships between subsystems such as the mobile base and any manipulators on it. For the semantic maps, the process of extending the basic concept of a vector-valued occupancy grid map into a full-featured simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) system has already begun, and will no doubt require further adaptations from the other system modules in the quest to extend this system with mobile manipulation capability.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

VLM	Vision–language Model
LLM	Large Language Model
HLP	High-level planning
LLP	Low-level planning

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